

NOTES

Tiliacoridine—A New Alkaloid from *Tiliacora racemosa* Colebr

A. K. Barua, (Miss) P. Chakrabarti and A. S. Dutta Gupta

The isolation of two alkaloids tiliacorine^{1,2,3} and tiliarine⁴ from *T. racemosa* Colebr was reported earlier. Recently Anjaneyulu *et al.*⁵ have reported the isolation of three other new alkaloids, tiliacorinine, nortiliacorinine A and nortiliacorinine B from the leaves of the same plant. We wish to report here the isolation of another new alkaloid called tiliacoridine from the leaves of *T. racemosa*.

Using a very tenacious process of column chromatography over silica gel and neutral alumina, we have been able to isolate from the crude alkaloidal fraction a very small quantity of tiliacoridine, m.p. 153–56° (dec.). Analytical values for tiliacoridine were unsatisfactory most probably due to retention of solvent of crystallization. Its molecular formula, C₃₀H₄₀O₈N₂, was however, determined by its molecular ion at m/e 664 (accompanied by doubly charged ion peak at m/e 332) and by the high resolution measurement of exact mass of the former. Its uv. spectrum, λ_{max} 292 mμ (log ε 3.94), λ_{min} 264 mμ (log ε 3.52) is very similar to that of tiliacorine and tiliarine and this indicated the probability of tiliacoridine being a bisbenzyl tetrahydroisoquinoline group of alkaloids. But unlike tiliacorine and tiliarine, tiliacoridine does not appear to contain any dibenzo-*p*-dioxan system as it did not give any blue colour with a mixture of concentrated sulphuric and nitric acid⁶.

The NMR spectrum (220 MHz, CDCl₃) of tiliacoridine shows the presence of three methoxyl groups (δ 3.99, 3.94 and 3.82 ppm) and eight aromatic protons but no N-CH₃ group.

Due to the extremely poor yield and difficulties in isolating tiliacoridine, no further work has yet been possible.

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Department of Chemistry,
Bose Institute,
Calcutta-9.

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